

DISCRETE STIFFNESS TAILORING FOR IMPROVED BUCKLING PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Continuously varying fibre angle across flat plates has analytically been shown to improve buckling performance by up to 60%. However, manufacture of such panels has so far used methods which have either high radius of curvature and low deposition rate (Continuous Tow Shearing) or low radius of curvature and medium deposition rate (Advanced Fibre Placement). Discrete Stiffness Tailoring (DST) is an alternative way of varying fibre angle to increase buckling performance that is compatible with current high rate deposition methods such as Advanced Tape Laying (ATL). DST uses discrete changes of angle within individual layers to effect variation in stiffness across a composite component at the cost of in-plane butt joints within layers. Two schemes of distribution are considered for tailoring stiffness across the width of a panel; (i) Half Seam; where half the layers in a laminate are subject to tailoring and (ii) Full Seam; where all layers are tailored. Compression testing of flat panels shows that DST can improve buckling stress for Full Seam by up to 16% for the simple example of redistributing material in a standard angle quasi-isotropic $[\pm 45/90/0]_{2S}$ laminate. Comparison of experimental results with standard buckling analyses (FEA, VICONOPT) indicates that DST results are predictable within the bounds of error introduced by experimental boundary conditions. Although no compression strength reductions were apparent in compression testing, tensile testing of seamed regions shows that improved buckling performance comes at the cost of reductions in transverse strength for Half Seam and Full Seam schemes. However, such reductions should be acceptable where loading is compression dominated and seams run parallel to the load.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ever present demand from the aerospace industry is driving efforts to realize the full potential of composite materials in terms of weight reduction and performance optimization. Previous work has shown that one aspect of this effort, buckling performance, can be improved by stiffness tailoring which, for example, can increase load in the vicinity of supports thereby reducing the need for stiffening. Theoretical parametric work conducted by Biggers et al. identified that the redistribution of very stiff (0° plies) to the outer regions of a compressive panel loaded uni-axially would produce an increase in the buckling load [1]. Subsequent work based on the idea of optimising the stiffness dependent of location in a panel has predominantly focused on using continuous fibre steering [2-4]. Dodwell et al. [5] have shown that if angle and ply thickness are simultaneously varied across the width of a compression panel, a weight saving of up to 40% can be achieved in laminated composite panels provided that fibre steering radius can be precisely controlled ($<30\text{mm}$). Continuous Tow Shearing (CTS) [6] is a method of fibre steering that can achieve such control, however it is not suited to high rate manufacture. This paper builds on work in which it has been demonstrated that equal weight savings may be achieved if as few as three discrete strips of straight fibres, each with a different fibre orientation, are used as an alternative to fibre steering.

In a laminate design using Discrete Stiffness Tailoring DST, thickness and ply angles can be altered discretely and simultaneously across the geometry of a structure. Optimised DST designs are theoretically able to achieve a 40% weight saving compared to an optimized straight fibre design with equal buckling performance [5]. DST is based on the idea of Automated Tape Laying (ATL) of bi-angle Non-Crimp Fabrics (NCFs) and has potential to offer significant manufacturing benefit. The one-dimensional ATL method [7] adopted by DST laminates can, theoretically, lay down material up to 4 times faster than a standard unidirectional lay-up where, for instance, $\pm 45^\circ$ plies require a change in the tape head laying orientation. Combining this method with the use of bi-angle NCFs the deposition rate can be eight times greater than currently achieved [7].

This initial study uses the DST concept to redistribute material within a standard ply quasi-isotropic (QI) laminate without loss of in-plane stiffness. Improvements in buckling performance are assessed using numerical and experimental methods.

Although both continuous and discrete fibre steering have been shown to improve buckling resistance, they also create regions of high stress that are susceptible to growth of damage. A similar tailoring approach using discontinuous plies was created by Vizzini, [8], although in the context of attempting to reduce free edge stresses through fibre angle alterations; and the butt regions were found to initiate failure of the coupons. In a DST laminate, the point at which one orientation terminates and another commences (a seam) creates vulnerability in the structure. Two different ways of staggering seams are proposed (see Fig. 1) and experimental and numerical tension testing is used to evaluate their impact on transverse tensile strength.

2 PANEL DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE

DST uses discrete angle variation to enable component manufacture where stiffness is tailored in different zones to enhance the buckling performance of the structure, see Fig. 1. Gürdal et al. [2] studied two cases of tow paths which linearly vary along the longitudinal x direction or the transverse y direction. They showed that, due to redistribution of the longitudinal compressive load N_x , fibre angle variation in the y direction is more efficient than variation in the x direction in the case of initial buckling.

Figure 1: (a) Plan view of a DST compression coupon showing idealised boundary conditions, panel dimensions and loading regime for buckling tests. Red dashed lines (not clear) indicate simply-supported boundary conditions. Tensile specimen design is shown underneath. (b) Plan view of DST tensile coupon. (c). Not-to-scale cross-sectional representations of the QI, Half Seam and Full Seam stacking sequences showing staggered seams. (d) Table of stacking sequences for each panel and both regions.

In this paper therefore, we focus on variation in the direction transverse to load, in order to achieve the best structural efficiency whilst retaining prismatic conditions required for VICONOPT analysis (see Section 3). Stacking sequences and panel design were based on the simple premise of redistributing 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° material (without altering relative volumes, based on stiffness redistribution concepts highlighted in [8]) in a balanced

symmetric quasi-isotropic laminate to bring about buckling performance improvements. Such a design experiment offers a simple to understand problem; using standard plies that demonstrate the potential for DST buckling improvements, while offering an example against which analysis methods can be tested. However, it is worth noting that these designs do not represent optimized performance. Two methods for creating seams were considered each offering different degrees of continuous support to the seams see Fig. 1. Panels were manufactured as per sequences and seam regions given in Fig. 1 using HTS40/977-2 material with material properties summarized in table 1. Regions A and B in Fig. 1 are partitioned by transitional regions where ply angles are altered. Ply orientations are altered over a 30mm wide region, with neighbouring seams being staggered by 10mm.

As the seam region is expected to introduce an inherent weakness in terms of transverse strength in the compression panels, three tensile coupons based on the buckling coupon designs were created, Fig. 1. The seamed tensile specimens are a half width strip of the compressive panel, with a single seam straddled by the Regions A and B as described in Fig.1.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSES FOR BUCKLING

In order to design and optimise DST panels efficiently in future, it must be proven that computationally efficient methods for assessing buckling performance and seam strength can be utilised or adapted for use with DST panels. As such, the methods for analysing buckling performance outlined below have deliberately been constrained to those that are in standard use and are (relatively in comparison to alternative methods) computationally efficient. The predictive capabilities of these models and thus their use in future design studies will form part of the discussion of this paper. Areas for improvement will be highlighted.

3.1 Buckling performance

Two methods are employed for determining buckling performance of the QI, Half Seam and Full Seam panels; Finite Elements and the finite strip program VICONOPT [9]. VICONOPT is a computationally efficient method, which is suitable for implementation with parallel computing methods. For panels and loadings that are prismatic in the x direction and under the assumption that there is no coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation (i.e. the \mathbf{B} matrix of classical lamination theory is null), VICONOPT provides infinite periodic solutions to the equilibrium equation that governs buckling;

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 4D_{23} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x \partial y^3} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{33}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + 4D_{13} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^3 \partial y} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} + \left(N_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} + N_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where N_x , N_y and N_{xy} are in-plane forces and D_{11} , D_{12} , D_{22} , D_{13} and D_{33} are the bending stiffness terms of classical lamination theory. Solution of Eq. (1) is via exact, periodic formulations [10] of the form:

$$w = f_1(y) \cos \frac{\pi x}{\lambda} - f_2(y) \sin \frac{\pi x}{\lambda} \quad (2)$$

where the functions $f_1(y)$ and $f_2(y)$ allow various boundary conditions to be applied on the longitudinal edges of panels, including free, simple, clamped and elastic supports. The half-wavelengths λ in Eq. (2) are defined by the length of the plate L divided by the number of half-wavelengths assumed along the length of the plate. VICONOPT divides the panel under investigation into strips across its width. In a DST panel each strip will have a different set of bending stiffnesses and, in the results that follow, 13 to 18 strips are used depending on the presence of transition regions. Buckling loading factors are derived through an eigenvalue analysis which is executed on the transcendental stiffness matrix derived from the solution of the governing differential equations of the constituent strips. The transcendental eigenproblem requires an iterative solution that is performed using the Wittrick-Williams algorithm [11]. The lowest buckling load found for a range of values of λ is taken as the critical buckling for the panel.

Most aerospace structures, such as wing and fuselage panels, are long compared with cross-sectional dimensions. Hence, Strip models, making prismatic assumptions in the solution of equation (3), are computationally efficient in many applications. Approaches that find buckling loads by minimizing potential energy for assumed mode shapes have been developed [12]. VICONOPT has previously been used to predict buckling performance of DST laminates and has shown that the distribution of alternative ply orientations within a flat panel has greater impact on delaying the onset of buckling than altering the thickness along the width [5].

Finite element buckling and strength analysis was carried out using commercially available software package ABAQUS™ Standard in order to (i) confirm the predictive capacity of VICONOPT simulations, (ii) investigate alternative boundary conditions, (iii) explore non-linear buckling behavior of the panels, and (iv) model the strength of the seams. Eigenvalue buckling analysis (perturbation method) [13] was used to estimate buckling stress and strain. Non-linear FEA continuation analysis [13] was used, for capturing the post-buckling path. Since the QI panel has a trivial fundamental path, an imperfection in the form of bifurcation mode having the lowest bifurcation load was applied to the mesh. An imperfection magnitude of $\delta_o = t_h/100$, where ‘ t_h ’ is the thickness of the laminate, was used. Solutions used the Riks (Arc length) [14] method based solver in ABAQUS. In case of the Half Seam and Full Seam panels, due to the material asymmetry in the transition zone, it is not necessary to force an artificial imperfection. Thus, for these cases it was sufficient to use the geometrically non-linear solver (employing Newton method) in ABAQUS [15] with incrementally increasing loads to capture the bifurcation point and post-buckling path.

For each panel the mesh consisted of 30360; 8-node doubly curved thick shell, quadratic reduced integration; S8R elements with edge length of around 1mm. A mesh convergence study was also carried to make sure that the mesh was appropriately converged. The complete panel was modelled as a single part with uniform mesh density. A lamina type [15] material definition was used for each layer and the orthotropic material constants for the unidirectional HTS40/977-2 CFRP are summarized below [16]. The layup sequence corresponding to each part for each region (as described in Fig 1(d)) was specified as part of the section definition in ABAQUS using the composite layup tool and by creating appropriate partitions for each zone.

3.2 Finite Element method for tensile strength

FEA prediction of the strength of the seam region within a DST panel and its relationship with ultimate strength of the panel is complicated as there is no proven methodology for progressive damage modelling specifically for such constructions and all existing methodologies e.g. cohesive zone modelling (CZM) [17], continuum damage mechanics (CDM) [18] and discrete damage mechanics (DDM) [18], have potential advantages and disadvantages. Most notably the CZM and CDM approaches pose computational challenges as well as a tendency for being mesh dependent. The DDM approaches although computationally more efficient are primarily limited to symmetric layups and for matrix cracking that grows parallel to fibres.

In this study, finite element analysis of DST panels under tension was carried out with a view to understanding the failure process. This was accomplished by studying the evolving stress state, resulting from the progressive damage growth from the seams that connects the regions of dissimilar stiffness. Thus, the motivation behind this FEA study was to inform the future development of models, capable of quickly predicting, the strength reduction in DST laminates. Such models will then allow the evaluation of various design alternates for optimization of DST panels.

The finite element simulations were carried out using commercially available software ABAQUS™/Standard. Geometrically non-linear (large displacement) analysis was carried out for modelling damage growth. The FEA model reported here utilized cohesive zone modelling (CZM) [17] for simulating both the inter-laminar and intra-ply (for the butt-seams that connect regions of dissimilar stiffness) crack growth within the seams. Other ply damage mechanisms were not modelled directly; rather the failure indices for these modes were evaluated during post processing at various load steps to understand the evolving nature of damage within the test panels. The model assumes a plane strain (in the y - z plane) representation of the tensile panel that was shown in Fig. 1. Each ply, its associated polymeric inter-laminar seam region as well as polymeric butt-seams that define the transition between sections of different stiffness (angle orientation) were modelled discretely and separate material models were defined for each zone.

The material behaviour for each ply was assumed linear-orthotropic. Although previous studies by Soutis et al. [16] suggest that this material shows highly nonlinear shear behaviour for the ± 45 plies under compression; it was decided not to include this description into material model for the tensile simulation because: (i) it was verified numerically that, in this case, shear stresses would remain below the material shear yield strength for the bulk of the specimen. (ii) increase of shear stress beyond the shear yield strength was later established to effect only the localized region around the butt-seams after the failure of these seams. (iii) it was established through these simulations that, in this case, the tensile strength of the ± 45 and 90 degree plies was reached before the onset of non-linear shear. Thus, accounting for non-linear shear of plies without accounting for ply failure would not affect the results significantly and would only overly complicate the model.

In order to simplify the modelling of seam failure, it was assumed that the crack propagation would take place purely within the inter-ply resin region (polymeric seam) as opposed to being an interface crack (de-cohesion failure). Hence, seams were modelled as a solid layer with embedded cohesive zone along the mid-plane of the seam. An isotropic material definition based on the material properties of Epoxy-977-2 was used for the solid region while the embedded cohesive zone was defined using a traction-separation law and mixed-mode failure governed through the BK-criteria. The material properties for all regions are given in Table 1.

Orthotropic Elastic Properties of UD HTS 40/977-2					
$E_{11T}(MPa)$	$E_{11C}(MPa)$	$E_{22}(MPa)$	ν_{12}	$G_{12} = G_{13}(MPa)$	$G_{23}(MPa)$
135405	112000	10300	0.3	5200	3430
Orthotropic Strength Properties of UD HTS 40/977-2					
$X_T(MPa)$	$X_C(MPa)$	$Y_T = Z_T(MPa)$	$Y_C = Z_C(MPa)$	$S_{XY} = S_{XZ} = S_{YZ}(MPa)$	
2540	1500	82	236	101	
Strength Properties of $[\pm 45]_{2S}$					
Tensile Strength (MPa)		In-Plane Shear Strength (MPa)		In-Plane Shear Yield (MPa)	
202		101		52	
Properties of Epoxy 977-2					
$E(MPa)$		ν		Normal Strength (MPa)	
3500		0.38		81	
Cohesive Zone Properties					
$K_n(N/mm^2)$	$K_t(N/mm^3)$	Normal Strength (MPa)	Shear Strength (MPa)	$G_{IC}(N/mm)$	$G_{IIC}(N/mm)$
1.00E+05	1.00E+05	60	80	0.352	1.45

Table 1: Summary of material properties [16, 19].

The details of the finite element mesh used for each of the zones (plies, inter-laminar seams and butt seams) are described in Table 2. As can be seen from this table a very refined mesh was necessary to capture the stress gradient between the zones of different stiffness accurately. The regions were all connected in one mesh for the specimen, using node based tie-constraints applied at mating surfaces (edges) between the regions.

Region	Element Type	Edge length along thickness, z-axis (μm)	Edge length along longitudinal direction, y-axis (μm)
Individual Plies	CPE4*	62.5	50
Interlaminar Seams	CPE4I**	4	5
	COH2D4***	4	5
Intra-ply (Butt) Seams	CPE4I**	18	25
	COH2D4***	18	25
Total number of elements in all regions: Full Seam			1.630 million
Total number of elements in all regions: Half Seam			1.629 million

* 4-node 2D plane strain linear quadrilateral elements

** 4-node 2D plane strain linear quadrilateral elements with incompatible mode

*** 4-node 2D cohesive elements (used with plane strain option)

Table 2: FEA Mesh details for the tensile damage model

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Compression testing of buckling panels was undertaken using an Instron 5585H machine at a displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min in the 0° direction of the coupons. Specimens were supported in a modified version (increased gauge width and height) of the test fixture described by ASTM D7137 [20] with the exception that loading edges were clamped to prevent ‘Brooming’ type end failures, see Fig. 1. All coupons were monitored with 6 strain gauges with positions given on Fig. 1. A spider 8 data acquisition system and Catman software [21], were used to capture Strain and load data. Strain gauge output was used to ensure correct alignment of coupons in the test machine such that pure axial compression would be applied. A Limes Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system employing a stereo pair of 1MP high speed Photron SA3 Cameras was used to track coupon strain and displacement in three dimensions. Post-processing was undertaken using correlated Solutions VIC3D software [22]. The panels were initially loaded to a point at which they had clearly buckled from live strain gauge observations, and then re-loaded two more times to discern if any damage or failure had occurred previously.

Tension coupons were tested under tension in the Instron 5585H machine with loading applied in the 90° ply direction as per Fig. 1. The full and half seam coupons were loaded at a fixed displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min, which was then increased to 0.6 mm/min in subsequent QI test. An extensometer and DIC system (as described above) were used to monitor strains.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Buckling performance

Table 1 gives FEA, VICONOPT and experimental results for buckling. Experimental buckling results were determined from analysis of strains from strain gauge data, presented in Fig. 3, to determine stiffness variation and bifurcation points indicating buckling. The solid strain lines are from the first buckling run, the dashed from subsequent re-loadings. The bifurcation point for each experimental test was determined by using the average strain data of all six gauges from the initial run data to locate the point at which a significant stiffness change was observed. At this point, the two linear regions either side of that kink were extrapolated until they crossed each other. The stress at which they met was taken as the buckling stress of the panel. Results in Fig. 3(d) show a comparison of average strain from the six gauges on each panel. FEA results are also plotted for comparison. Lower values of pairs of symbols relate to use of a simply-supported boundary condition on the loading edge in the numerical analyses; an attempt to capture real experimental boundary conditions. Results were confirmed by analysis of the point of formation of buckling mode shapes in DIC images, see Fig. 4. Comparative buckling mode shapes from FEA are shown for both the pinned and clamped cases in Fig. 4, for the QI panel. The Half and Full seam analytical mode shapes are identical to those produced from the QI analysis. VICONOPT modeshapes were identical to the FEA modeshapes.

Panel Name	QI			Half Seam			Full Seam		
	VIC	FEA	Exp.	VIC	FEA	Exp.	VIC	FEA	Exp.
Buckling Load P^C (kN)	88- 121	84-110	92	101-136	94-120	96	102-142	96-124	117
Buckling Effective Stress (MPa)	123- 170	118-154	131	141-192	132- 169	134	143-199	134-174	149
Buckling Strain ϵ^C (μ strain)	2785- 3828	2592- 3390	2361	3260- 4409	2944- 3777	2515	3548- 4939	3212- 4155	3478

Table 3. Buckling results from VICONOPT and FEA simulations and compression tests. Lower bounds on numerical results relate to simply supported loading boundaries. Upper bounds are for clamped loading edges. In both cases non-loading edges are simply supported. VICONOPT and FEA use the length between the supports (165mm) for calculating stress, whereas the experimental results use the full length (175mm).

Figure 2: Stress vs. strain results based on strain gauge readings for (a) QI panel, (b) Half Seam panel and (c) Full Seam panel; insets indicate the position of strain gauges on the panels. Pale dotted results are results of re-testing of the panel. (d) Dotted lines show average experimental strain based on all six gauges vs stress for the first test on each panel. Solid lines are the results of averaging of non-linear FEA strains taken at the same locations as the strain gauges.

Figure 3: DIC images of out-of-plane deflection indicating the emergence of buckling mode shapes (a) QI (b) Half Seam and (c) Full Seam. The stresses (in MPa) at which these images were recorded are given in the bottom right corner. The buckling mode shapes for the QI panel, obtained in FEA, with pinned and clamped boundary conditions are shown to the right of the DIC images.

4.2 Tensile Strength

Figure 4 (a) presents the nominal stress versus strain curve for the experiment and the FEA simulation. In Fig. 4 experimental strains for the full and half seam coupons are derived from DIC images taken at positions in Regions A and B defined in Fig. 1. The QI coupon displayed uniform strain along the length of the specimen. The location from which the strains were extracted are approximately the centreline of the coupon; at 25mm and 75mm along the gauge length. FEA strains were measured from the corresponding locations of ply 1 (lower most ply – tool side), for both the half seam and full seam cases. Fig. 4 (b) describes the evolution of damage in seams (both inter-laminar and butt seam) with increasing load (nominal stress) evaluated from FEA. Only the largest seam damage zone within the specimen is shown. The upper three figures show damage in the full seam specimen at nominal stress levels of 51 MPa, 162 MPa and 234 MPa respectively. These stress levels correspond to the initiation of damage in the butt-seam, initiation of damage in inter-laminar seam and the maximum seam damage observed in the FEA simulation respectively. The region shown corresponds to the butt interface between the 0° and -45° zones of the bottom ply (ply1). The butt seam in this case is within the transition zone (55 mm from the start of zone A) and the inter-laminar seam is bounded above by the $+45^\circ$ zone of ply 2 (not shown).

The lower three figures in Fig. 4(b) show damage in the half seam case at nominal stress levels of 64 MPa, 255 MPa and 462 MPa respectively. Again, these stress levels correspond to the initiation of damage in the butt-seam, initiation of damage in inter-laminar seam and the maximum seam damage observed in in the FEA simulation respectively. In this case the region shown corresponds to the butt interface between the 0° and -45° zones of the ply 10. The butt seam in this case is at the end of transition zone (65 mm from the start of zone A) and the inter-laminar seam is bounded by the 90° zone of ply 11 (not shown) above and the $+45^\circ$ zone of ply 9 (not shown) below.

Figure 4: (a) FEA and experimental strain vs. stress results for the tensile coupon tests. Regions A and B are described in Fig. 1. (b) Growth of seam damage (in butt as well as inter-laminar seams) predicted using FEA.

Surface ply strain for key points during the tensile tests are shown in Figure 5(a) using a set of DIC images. In Figure 5(b) the through-thickness failure index (FI) for each ply has been plotted using FEA results. The failure index is based on max longitudinal stress criteria $FI = \frac{\sigma_{yy}}{S^\theta}$ where, σ_{yy} is the longitudinal stress at each integration point within a ply and S^θ is the longitudinal strength of the ply at a particular orientation θ . Thus, for a $\pm 45^\circ$ ply, $S^\theta = 202\text{MPa}$, for a 90° ply, $S^\theta = 82\text{MPa}$, and for a 0° ply, $S^\theta = 2540\text{MPa}$ (see Table 2). A value of ≥ 1 indicates onset of damage within the ply and < 1 indicates that the ply is undamaged.

Figure 5: (a) DIC planar images of tensile strains developed during the Half Seam and Full Seam tests. The images show the discrete stiffness tailoring in terms of different strains developed in different halves of the coupons. The stresses (in MPa) are given in the bottom right of each image. (b) Cross-section images from the FEA analysis showing failure of the butt seams and plies.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Buckling performance

VICONOPT results in Table 3 show that whilst maintaining the same amount of material (including the same angle orientation) as the baseline QI panel, DST can increase the buckling strains by approximately 29%, and load by as much as 17%. Similar results in Table 3 for FEA analyses confirm this prediction.

The experimental buckling results in Fig. 2 confirm the advantage of using DST as predicted using VICONOPT and FEA, with an increased buckling load of 4.5% using the Half Seam design, and 27% using the Full Seam. This is equivalent to a buckling stress increase of 2% and 14% respectively. There is an inherent difficulty in determining the precise bifurcation point for each test, and so the possibility of error in these quoted results must be acknowledged, but they are seen to support the analytical design theory.

The QI experimental compressive moduli of the panels was found to be 26% higher than the analytical results and 22% higher than FEA, comparing the pinned results. FEA also produces lower buckling load and stress values, matching VICONOPT to within 13%. This can be accounted for by varying boundary conditions; as in FEA, the vertical supports induce a secondary stress in the panel due to Poisson's ratio. In VICONOPT however, the strain is applied within the panel and no transverse stress is assumed. The boundaries modelled in experimental testing are never perfect and it can be assumed that the simple vertical supports are more rigid in reality, causing the effective compressive modulus to increase. From the comparison of analytical models and experimental buckling results, it can be seen that VICONOPT can be used reliably as a quick design tool for future work seeking to optimise DST panels and structures, as it can predict the performance difference.

The experimental DIC out-of-plane displacements, Fig. 3, show that the buckling mode shapes initiated from the lower half of the DST panels before forming centrally. This is indicative of a boundary condition that is somewhere between simple supported and clamped, as can be seen in Fig. 3, where both pinned and clamped scenarios are provided. When comparing the experimental and analytical results, the pinned condition seems to provide the best estimate, with all VICONOPT and FEA results falling within 10% of the experimentally obtained values. The roughly central, half-wavelength buckling mode shapes, as seen in each test, is consistent with the analytical predictions.

The panels were loaded beyond the predicted buckling loads; and the QI and Full Seam panels failed at the top boundary. From the stress strain plots in Fig 2, it can be seen at roughly 55-60 MPa for the Half and Full Seam panels there are horizontal kinks in the data from the initial tests (solid lines). These were not observed in the re-runs or in any of the QI tests, so would indicate that this is something peculiar to the seamed panels. It is likely that failure of butt joints in the seam region these kinks. However, any failure in that region did not result in delamination growth or propagation, and had very limited effect on the buckling capacity or stiffness of the panel.

5.2 Tensile strength

Failure of the QI coupon was as expected; a sudden failure at the mid-section of the coupon, see Fig 5(a). The loading behaviour was linear up until the point of failure. For the Half Seam however, the coupons exhibited somewhat non-linear response towards the end of the test; starting around 364 MPa with complete catastrophic failure around 384 MPa, see Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Some nonlinearity (drop in stress) can also be seen midway through the test (between 180 – 200 MPa) for region B in Fig. 4. This seems to have stemmed from the failure of ± 45 plies which occurred immediately after failure of the butt-seam. The FEA confirms this assertion as Fig. 5(b) shows significant matrix cracks in ± 45 regions around the butt-seams at a stress level of 212 MPa. The fact that the butt-seam crack initiated earlier can be seen from Fig 4(b), where the cracks initiate around 50 MPa and grow to full failure at around 255 MPa nominal stress. The FEA, Fig 5(b), shows that the cracking in ± 45 plies continues through the thickness, with surface plies cracking much later for the Half Seam specimen. FEA also shows that the failure of continuous 90° plies in Region B takes place at around 360MPa, Fig 5(b). This correlates well with the experimentally observed non-linear response for region B at around 364 MPa. Since progressive damage was only modelled for seams (interfaces), Fig. 4, the non-linear response observed in the experiment after this load cannot be replicated by FEA. The failure index however confirms that this is indeed what would one expect if progressive damage of plies was also included within the model. It also indicates that the after the onset of failure in 90° plies in region B one would expect a catastrophic (sudden) failure as the ± 45 plie have already failed according to FEA and the only two plies holding the specimen integrity are the two continuous zero degree plies. Thus, in the experiment the Half Seam specimen showed a final failure at a stress 46% lower than the QI coupon. The final failure was sudden, with a complete drop in the stress registered at failure, Fig. 4(a) and 5(a).

The Full Seam coupon was affected almost immediately by loading, see Fig. 4(a), and reached a peak stress value 76% lower than the QI control. After this peak was reached, the coupon displayed a very gradual pseudo-ductile failure as intra-ply cracks developed in the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and butt seams close to the centre of the transition region failed, see Fig. 5(a). The FEA is less accurate for the full-seam case. The stress-strain response in region A, (0/90) is captured accurately but does not capture the response in region B. This is likely a consequence of the model's inability to account for the progressive damage and a highly non-linear in-plane shear behaviour of region B as is also reported for this material in earlier studies [15, 18]. The FEA, however seems to capture the onset of butt-

seam failure accurately as well as the onset of failure of the ± 45 plies (see Fig. 4(b) and Fig. 5(b)) in terms of corresponding stress levels in tests as well as the location of most significantly damaged seam. These results indicate that for more accurate damage prediction for the tensile case, using FEA, the model must also account for progressive ply damage. The model presented here is still useful however, as it accurately indicated the damage in seams as well as stress levels at which final failure was expected to occur. The FEA has also provided insight that in future any DST optimization of panel performance for buckling will not be severely restricted by failure of butt-seams only; as the failure of these seams do not necessarily trigger an immediate failure of the laminate. Thus, although some compromise on strength is inevitable the laminate can be designed to have sufficient transverse tensile strength by careful inclusion of load bearing continuous plies.

From these results, it is obvious that there is a significant reduction in transverse strength that needs to be accepted as a consequence of the increased buckling performance, particularly for the Full Seam scheme. It is worth noting that this design of this experiment was to prove and quantify the use of DST as a performance enhancer. The initial design phase did not include any optimisation of the structure or ply angles used for either increased buckling performance or the seam strength. Future work will need to include a simplistic way of analysing seam strength for design. These regions within a structure can localise failure, which although in many cases is not ideal; for certification purposes this could be advantageous, as damage could be expected to be contained within the seam region before any other part of the structure failed, aiding inspection. For loading cases where uni-axial compressive load dominates and the seams run parallel to the load, this magnitude of reduction in strength due to DST may not be critical.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Use of Discrete Stiffness Tailoring (DST) to affect simple redistribution of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° material (whilst maintaining the volume of each) has been shown, in comparison to a $[45/-45/90/0]_{2S}$ laminate, to improve buckling performance both experimentally and numerically by up to 2% and 14% respectively. Differences in FEA and VICONOPT results for buckling performance are within 13%, both capture relative performance differences between control, Half and Full Seam DST panels to $<5\%$ and both agree with experimental values to within 10% when pinned horizontal boundaries conditions are applied. Compression results thus indicate that DST improves buckling performance and that the computationally efficient buckling analysis program VICONOPT is sufficiently accurate to be used in initial design studies. When aligned perpendicular to compression loading, in-plane seams created by the DST process are seen to have limited effect on buckling performance and compression strength/modulus despite local failure of the intra-ply butt joint. In contrast, when aligned parallel to tensile loading, reductions in strength are seen for laminates where 50% or 100% of plies contain seams respectively. However, the residual strength implied by these tests, the pseudo-ductile response of the Full Seam coupon and the likely ratio of primary and secondary loadings on aerospace components indicates that DST should be a suitable manufacturing process for improving laminate structural efficiency. In order to avoid extremely costly FEA analyses, design with DST will require derivation of novel strength prediction models. Work in this area will continue as part of the EPSRC project "ADAPT" that aims to using stiffness tailoring to improve buckling performance and increase production rates of defect free composite components.

Future work will focus on (i) repeated testing to prove statistical significance of results, (ii) analytical modelling for seam strength, (iii) optimization of boundary free structures such as box sections for buckling performance and minimum mass.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S.B. Biggers & S. Srinivasan, Compression Buckling Response of Tailored Rectangular Composite Plates. *AIAA Journal*, **31**, 1993, No. 3, pp. 590-596.

- [2] Z. Gurdal & R. Olmedo, In-Plane Response of Laminates with Spatially Varying Fiber Orientation: Variable Stiffness Concept. *AIAA Journal*, **31**, 1993, No. 4, pp. 751-758.
- [3] M.W. Hyer & R.F. Charette, The Use of Curvilinear Fiber Format in Composite Structure Design. *AIAA*, 1989. Paper No. 1989-1404.
- [4] E. Lund, Buckling Topology Optimization of Laminated Multi-Material Composite Shell Structures. *Composite Structures*, **91**, 2009, pp. 158-167.
- [5] T.J. Dodwell, R. Butler & A.T Rhead, Optimum Fiber Steering of Composite Plates for Buckling and Manufacturability. *AIAA Journal*, **54**, 2016, No.3, pp. 1139-1142.
- [6] S.W. Tsai & J.D.D. Melo, Composite Materials Design and Testing: Unlocking mystery with invariants. Stanford, CA: Composites Design Group, Department of Aeronautics & Astronautics, Stanford University, 2015. pp. 385-420.
- [7] B.C. Kim, K. Potter & P. Weaver, Continuous Tow Shearing for Manufacturing Variable Angle Tow Composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **43**, 2012, No. 8, pp. 1347-1356.
- [8] A.J. Vizzini, Strength of Laminated Composites with Internal Discontinuities Parallel to the Applied Load. *AIAA Journal*, **30**, 1992, No. 6, pp. 1515-1520.
- [9] F.W. Williams, D. Kennedy, R. Butler & M.S. Anderson, VICONOPT: Program for Exact Vibration and Buckling Analysis of Prismatic Plate Assemblies. *AIAA Journal*, **1**, 1991, No. 4, pp. 497-518.
- [10] W.H. Wittrick & F.W. Williams. Buckling and Vibration of Anisotropic or Isotropic Plate Assemblies under Combined Loadings. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, **16**, 1974, pp. 209-239.
- [11] W.H. Wittrick & F.W. Williams, An Algorithm for Computing Critical Buckling Loads of Elastic Structures. *Journal of Structural Mechanics*, **1**, 1973, No. 4, pp. 497-518.
- [12] D.J. Dawe & T.J. Craig, Buckling and vibration of shear deformable prismatic plate structures by a complex finite strip method. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, **30**, 1988, No. 2, pp. 77-99.
- [13] E.J. Barbero, *Finite Element Analysis of Composite Materials Using Abaqus™*, Chapter 4: Buckling. CRC Press, 2013.
- [14] E. Riks, An incremental approach to the solution of snapping and buckling problems. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **15**, 1979, No. 7, pp. 529-551.
- [15] ABAQUS, *ABAQUS™ Theory Manual*, Version 6.17. Dassault Systemes Simulia Corp.
- [16] A. Jumahat, C. Soutis, F.R. Jones & A. Hodzic, Fracture mechanisms and failure analysis of carbon fibre toughened epoxy composites subjected to compressive loading. *Composite Structures*, **92**, 2009, No. 2, pp. 295-305.
- [17] R.S. Choudhry, S.F. Hassan, S. Li & R. Day, Damage in single lap joints of woven fabric reinforced polymeric composites subjected to transverse impact loading, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **80**, 2015, pp. 76-93.
- [18] E.J. Barbero, *Finite Element Analysis of Composite Materials Using Abaqus™*, Chapter 8: Continuum Damage Mechanics & Chapter 9: Discrete Damage Mechanics. CRC Press, 2013.
- [19] A. Atas & C. Soutis, Strength prediction of bolted joints in CFRP composite laminates using cohesive zone elements. *Composites: Part B*, **58**, 2014, pp. 25-34.
- [20] ASTM International. Standard test for compressive residual strength properties of damaged polymer matrix composite plates. ASTM D7137/D7137M-07.
- [21] HBM, 'catman Data Acquisition Software' (2017). <https://www.hbm.com/en/2290/catman-data-acquisition-software/> [Accessed 02/06/2017]
- [22] Correlated Solutions, 'VIC-3D System.' <http://www.correlatedsolutions.com/vic-3d> [Accessed 18/05/17].